

Innovations and Advantages of Kingred KD Series EDM Wire Cutting Machine

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Annotation. Diversity of cultures is one of the characteristics of modern social life. Development of multicultural education in such an environment is an important task of education. This thesis examines the organization of educational processes in multicultural education by developing appropriate principles. In addition, while studying the theoretical and practical aspects of the methods of developing multicultural competence, the differences and similarities between them were considered.

Key words: CNC system, ergonomic, compact, autotechnologist, rigidity design, surface roughness, the windows based, intuitive interface.

Specially designed CNC system

The Windows-based CNC system has a built-in KCUT CAM system with an intuitive interface that allows you to create a control program on the machine without using additional software, and the built-in "Autotechnologist" function will select the optimal cutting modes by itself.

The CNC rack is equipped with an ergonomic and operator-friendly touch display.

Compact ergonomic design

Solid bed with high rigidity design

The "C"-shaped structure with an upper column without voids eliminates the appearance of deformation, which is more rigid than the "F"-shaped structure.

Cast bed made of high-quality HT250 cast iron.

Due to the advantages described above, the EDM wire cutting machines of the KD series on a new generation of molybdenum wire make it possible to obtain the highest machining accuracy for machines in this segment in the Russian market with maximum stability and ease of adjustment.

- Linear machining accuracy up to ± 0.006 mm
- Cone machining accuracy up to ± 0.015 mm
- Best surface roughness Ra 0.8
- The angle of inclination of the wire from + 12

List of used literature:

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